

Total Quality Management in Higher education

Bijay Lal Pradhan¹, Sanjeeb Sangroula² and Tika Ram Chalise³

Tribhuvan University, Nepal,

Network for Quality Productivity and Competitiveness Nepal (NQPCN)

*Corresponding Author: bijayprad@gmail.com, Telephone Number +977-9855030302

Abstract

Quality is more than just a state of mind; it's a foundational perspective that shapes how we perceive and respond to various situations. Quality, in essence, emerges from the fusion of human expertise and material resources. It translates to outperforming ourselves today compared to yesterday and priming ourselves for an even better tomorrow. Quality isn't something that occurs by chance; it's a result of thoughtful and intelligent efforts. It's about not only achieving quality but also sustaining the level we've achieved.

Numerous factors contribute to the cultivation of quality education. A mission statement stands as a testament to an institution's commitment to education, research, and its broader impact on society. This declaration plays a pivotal role in the relentless pursuit of excellence. Faculty and subject matter experts form the bedrock of educational quality. The process of upholding quality is ascertained by accreditation, which serves as a vital pillar in ensuring that education maintains its high standards.

At the heart of TQM lies an enduring culture of continuous improvement. This culture drives the institution's ongoing quest to refine aspects such as the admission process, the creation of a safe and conducive learning environment, strengthening student-faculty relationships, and the effective management of stakeholders. Additionally, the focus extends to crucial aspects like job placement, fostering a culture of learning, and more.

Navigating TQM within higher education is a complex endeavor, shaped by external influences and divergent perspectives on what quality defines. However, it remains an indispensable pursuit, as it's the means through which we harness our resources to yield quality education. In this pursuit, the faculty's role, adept stakeholder management, and a steadfast commitment to continuous improvement emerge as fundamental pillars. In addition, the opportunities and challenges posed by AI cannot be overlooked when it comes to upholding educational quality.

Institutions can amplify their commitment to quality by establishing and nurturing learning centers, which serve as vibrant hubs for education. Moreover, orientation programs can be designed to ease the transition for international students, ensuring they feel welcomed and supported. Ultimately, the crux of the matter is to foster an environment where quality is not merely achieved but perpetually nurtured.

Keywords: Quality, Education, Continuous Improvement, Faculty, Stakeholder Management

1.1 Introduction

This session deals with background, general overview and outlook of this research work. The relevant importance of this research has also been discussed in this session. Besides the research objective, research questions and research rational and problems have been discussed in detail.

Background

It is a universal truth that the universities and colleges have been instrumental in manifestation and delivery of knowledge to society at large since history. (Anninos, 2007) argues that from “ancient Athens the ages of Plato people gathered and organized them in academia and interacted with deep interest towards systematic academic pursuit”. Bowden and Matron (1998) claims universities and colleges roles as a primary actor involves in higher learning and education. Dr. Benjamin S (Bloom Taxonomy of Learning) provides substantial insights in the individual and institutional learning as process (also referred to as Blooms Ladder of Learning) emphasizing that learning process in the higher education and learning is prominent with different levels of Blooms ladder of learning as represented in figure 1.

Figure 1.1 : Blooms Taxonomy of Learning

Though higher education around globe is criticized in continuous fashion as lacking scientific edge and intelligent element in terms of their essential “purpose” of significant contribution and goals, the expansion and establishment of higher education is profound (Clarke, 2008) and claimed that most part of world higher education contemporarily apply quantitative methodologies, statistical tools and scientific approach towards higher education decision makings. Lorange (2005) argues that though many higher education’s proclaim offerings innovative and scientific higher education, but in reality, at many higher education’s only offers typical higher education implying that majority of higher education offerings are little differentiated with each other with little exception in this industry.

Cornuel (2005) stress that the role of higher education in today’s “global era and G-Local economy” is to deliver students with the necessary higher education skills and capabilities to be a competent higher education leader and stress that the higher education ought to be crucially responsible to foster the institutionalization process of private and public organization enabling them to growth. (Blackmore, 2002; Peters, 2004) In context of educational reforms to attain educational quality and students learning quality, the higher learning institutions quality reforms are propelled by the rapid globalization and meeting the expectations of global communities to challenge the traditional knowledge with contemporary skills and developing the generic capabilities

This research works intends to explore “Total Quality Management” in higher education schools. For this we need to clearly determine the “basic purposes and reason for existence of the higher education which would give us a clear concept about the “mission and purpose” of this established institution. The small synopsis of higher education discussed above will enlighten this study for the exploring the Total Quality management issues in higher education in general and have highlighted the importance of higher educational establishment to with an aim to pursuit of academic knowledge and manifestations of such knowledge in society growth and development.

1.2 Objective of the study

This study intends to explore “Total Quality Management in higher education” and specifically a case study with emphasis to operational process, quality system and practices at x higher education school. Therefore, the research aims to study:

- ✓ To find out and appraise and evaluate quality systems at higher education with existing total quality management frameworks and models.
- ✓ To study the operational process of higher education and finds scope for continuous improvement.
- ✓ To identify problems and challenges of Quality systems in higher education and to recommend measures to address them.
- ✓ To derive the components of TQM in higher education with references to higher learning.

1.3 Research questions

The researchers has to move in certain direction which he/she ought to in-order to objectively study what he/she is intended. The research questions will enable and continuously enlighten the path and direction for this research. The following are major research questions that a researcher is looking for answer.

- ✓ What is TQM
- ✓ How is TQM implemented?

- ✓ Who are the stakeholders of a college?
- ✓ How do the stakeholders measure quality?
- ✓ How could college/universities use this information to evaluate quality control systems?
- ✓ How can a TQM system be integrated into a College Control Management System?
- ✓ How can we appraise and evaluate quality management system at college?

1.4 Research Rationale

Having some years experiences in academic institution has certainly led the researchers in understanding some of the issues that are critical to achieving success and achieving excellence in higher education. The conceptual skill and ability i.e., ability to conceive a “big mental picture” depends largely on the academic exposure as well as handful of experiences and thinking grooms the individual with essential skills to become future education industry leaders. With this notion in mind, it was choice of researcher to academically pursue the study in regards to “Total Quality Management” in higher learning with emphasis to higher education. The subject matter “Continuous improvements” and “Total Quality Management” fascinates the researchers and presume that it is interesting subject in general. Higher education has many challenges at the moment but aims to destine those successes by thriving on the quality market offering competition. Higher education is promising organization that offers Higher –levels higher education qualification and training.

2. Literature review

2.1 Introduction

The academic approach foundations and pillar of Total Quality Management are: history and quality Guru’s conceptual framework and theories (vision), internationally recognized and universally accepted Total Quality Management models, arithmetical tools, and contemporary management practices.

2.2 Literature Review: Brief Background

The word “Quality” as argued by (Sahney, et al., 2004) originated from “qualis” a Latin word implying a meaning “What kind of”. Feigenbaum (1951) quality as “value” Crosby (1979) quality imply “conformance to requirements” and “defects avoidance” and “fitness for use” (Juran and Gryna, 1988) “surpassing customers’ expectations” (Parshuraman et al., 1985) and Quality as synonym for “excellence (Peters and Waterman, 1995). The different views on quality have led to opening a thought that “quality” is relative and contextual (Sahney , et al., 2004).

Talha (2004) and Tari (2005) broadly states the TQM address organizational-wide entire transformational process and activities of pdt/services such as supply chain, process control, conformance to quality and principle of continuous improvements meeting and enhancing customer values creation addition and delivery and customer satisfaction.

Source: Hellsten and Klefsjö (2000)

Figure 2.0: TQM as management system adapted from Svensson and Klefsjo” (2006)

2.3 Origin of TQM and Gurus

The Prominent work of the Japanese Management Quality Guru Kaoru Ishikawa shaped the term Quality as “companywide quality control”. Ishikawa (1985) works on quality control focused on synthesizing Quality as “holistic and totality” and practiced “Companywide quality control”.

While the work of Feigenbaum (1956) stretched the term “quality Control” to the various dimensions of quality such as development, maintenance and continuous improvements of quality. He further urged that “Total Quality control is effective system for integrating these above-mentioned dimensions of quality as synergistic efforts of different group of people enabling customer satisfaction”.

But Today Total Quality Management (TQM) is universal and pervasive concept in organisation creating competitive edge and delivering quality services and products (Kekale and Kekale , 1995). Motwani et al., (2005) argues that service –oriented and product- oriented organization are tremendously interested towards applying TQM. Martínez-Lorent et al., (1998) affirm that large numbers of organisations are applying TQM and it is widely discussed in academic study. Powel (1995) writes that TQM evolution could be traced and linked to year 1949, post-World War II where Japanese formed a committee of scholars representing Japanese engineers, scientist and government official whose sole objective was “improving productivity and quality”.

Edward Deming strongly tried to pursued that quality should be observed using numerical and statistical tools in work place and emphasize on designing of proactive process control rather than inspection. Deming’s 14 principles for enhancing quality improvement essentially revolves around organisational leaderships, institutionalising quality improvements as core philosophy and purpose, superior inputs resources at beginning to final production process, capacity building of staffs through development program, identifying flawless organisational communication aimed at fostering co-operation and promoting qualitative goals (Naylor, 2002, p.511). Crosby (1979) a prominent quality guru replenished quality literature by revitalized “Zero Defects” ideas towards ‘TQM’ and ruled out quality is “Conformance to Requirements”. Crosby (1979) mantras sensibly point out that no defects are acceptable and this approach helped employees in reframing mental disposition towards quality and stringently supported the notion that quality requirements should constantly exists as privilege concern (Larry, 1991).

2.4. Definition of TQM/Continuous improvements

Sea Law (2010) argues that for achieving nearer and probably clearer pictures of total quality in higher education academy it is significant to explore and derive towards the direction of compiling the researchers upon the subject matter “total quality and critically examining the different perspectives and definitions of Total quality Management in educational institution in general. Tam (2001) upholds quality as concept in academic institutions often referred by him as stakeholders-relative.

2.5. Total Quality management in higher education

During the 1980s the higher learning higher education and university slowly started accepting the TQM principles and philosophy. At 1980s TQM growth and application in higher learning was in crawling stages. Post 1980s the universities and colleges were influx through TQM principle and philosophies. (Brigham, 1994; Ewell, 1993; Zemsky *et al.*, 1993, cited in Pariseau and McDaniel (1995) argues that the rapid growth of TQM centred quality program in higher education schools and universities was result of mounting pressure from higher education stakeholders and dissatisfaction of various constituencies (Golhar and Ahire, 1994) including faculty, alumni, employers, students, parents to address the rising gap concern from customers about improving services quality, fiscal circumstances and growing competition and actual performances. Pariseau and McDaniel (1995) specifically put that higher education school ought to give paramount importance to total quality culture, practices and quality services being committed to

fascinating principles of TQM known as “continuous improvements” to address the higher education stakeholders needs and expectations known as institutional constituencies.

Some important stakeholders (especially Faculty members) debated against the ideas of extensively adopting and integrating TQM in higher academic institution (Entin, 1993; Ewell, 1993; Horine *et al.*, 1993; Marchese, 1993 cited in Pariseau and McDaniel (1995) stating that TQM has could not address the problems academic institution were facing and blamed TQM Philosophy for not producing the desire results as expected in academia industry.

Chan (1994) argues that for “higher education “to be fit for usage as Juran said, fit to industry one aspects of quality management is to congruence the direction of management teaching and corporate and industry desires. (Golhar and Ahire, 1994) affirms that in higher education the concept of customer orientation, process focus, teamwork, quality planning and monitoring, continuous improvements and empowerment are key constituent elements of TQM

Harvey and Knight (1996) argue that in the context of post-secondary education the quality concepts should be broadly applied and understood as concepts for transformation as core and central for improving higher education quality.

Harvey and Knight (1996) profoundly believed that Quality concepts in academic higher education institution should be bounded by “concepts of transformation” as central and core. While (Tam, 2001) in general is of that view that student experiences ought to have more space occupied in towards “quality concepts” in academic institutions.

Richardson (2000) prefers the student learning as crucially important concepts in particular context. Bogue (1998) identifies four elements as key to managing “quality approaches” contemporarily and they are, firstly accreditation and program reviews which demands the close examination and evaluation of existing program and external standards.

Bogue (1998) profoundly believe that in nurturing total quality in colleges and universities, should be transcending beyond each responsibility through a developing a feeling of community having passion, dedication and caring for quality by such community to address total quality from its ethical and moral dimension too.

Pariseau and McDaniel (1995) specifies that for higher education the students (customers) higher involvement and cooperation is of paramount important for creating services. In their research they found that “assurance” is the key words for higher education implying to many other vocabularies meaning “knowledge”, “courtesy” and capabilities that fosters trust and confidence. Also, these factors are of most important in any educational setup for TQM.

Similarly, Fox (1991, p.10) point out the need of and role “TQM steering committee” comprising “quality champions”, “Quality sponsor” and “TQM Coordinator” by developing organization vision, setting quality objectives, allocation of quality budgets and role of leaderships for integrating quality ethos.

Piper (1993) argues that contextually quality in higher education is accepted and conceives as “institutional innovation” and continuous improvements. Pariseau and McDaniel (1995) in their research work at USA carried in two university found put “faculty” and “higher education schools” could not deliver quality in the eyes of students hinting a situation of “differences in perception of services quality. They opined that “higher education school” are remarked with adopting “faculty education program” and benchmark faculties’ performance in the area of services quality and customer satisfaction. AACSB, 2002; Lorange, 2003 argues that higher education which offers research and management program ought to have high caliber faculties able to create quality students are crucial in terms of reputations of higher education in academic and corporate society.

Konidari and Abernot (2006) argues that academic institutions could achieve their objectives only by combining TQM and organizational learning philosophies through employee empowerment, developing a professional community and developing a network of knowledge management in micro level backed by the mechanism for reevaluation of methodology to inquiry about professional introspection.

2.6 Recent Trends in Higher Education

Handen et al., 2009, Hoffman and Woody (2008) argue that most of the organization are majorly responsible to degrade the environment in this case universities are one of them. For the Dean and other responsible decision-making bodies, the major argument is about the healthy environmental practices and fundamental role of higher education in promoting the scientific knowledge about environmental management practices. Kusler (2009) defines “Lean UNIVERSITY offers a variation of the manufacturing principles in the education setting”.

Steve Kreidler, University of central Okhlahoma Executive Vice President, clarifies on the issues of importance of lean concept and principle in colleges and universities in the sense and in reality, to be able to put all the resources towards students This will led to understanding (process, operations, activities) anything that going in campus if not student focused are merely a wastage.

Emiliani (2004) argues the concept of lean and its application in designing the higher education school courses and delivering it to improves the graduate satisfaction levels with mentioning clearer expectation from students in regards specific guidelines and assignment standards by the professors and also in regards to applying specific teaching methodology, designing course study objectives, course materials and course structure and contents

2.7 Stakeholders Analysis

Freeman's (1986, 46) define stakeholder- "*any group or individual who can affect or is affected by the achievement of the organization's objectives*". Mitchell et al., (1997) argues that in order to identify and define stakeholders in any organization the study and analysis of their “possession” or certain attributes(qualities) enjoyed by them is essential. Such elements which tried to identify stakeholders in organizations are the “ability” or “power” of a stakeholder to “influence” the organization, the “legal” and “official” relationships of stakeholders towards firms and extent to which stakeholders can claim towards organization (for. e.g., claiming immediate attention).

The compilation work on the various definition on stakeholders’ analysis by Mitchell et al., (1997) has been substantial to enlighten the different definition, purview and context and issues in regards to stakeholders in any organization. The table below presents the different views and contribution of authors towards stakeholders’ analysis

Cavico and Mujtaba, (2009) argues that “principal establishment purpose to any higher education are manifesting values to student. From the above argument student has “value” interest from higher education school as student (both MBA and other management discipline, and research fellow, are significant stakeholders to higher education school. As mentioned by Vidaver-Cohen (2007), there are ranges of stakeholders in a higher education and as the stakeholder’s category differs so does the interest and stake of the stakeholders differs (Mitchell et al., 1997). In the higher learning the student attends the higher education school to receive values (Cavico and Mujtaba, 2009). of study (Vidaver-Cohen 2007).

Gulikers et al., 2009 argues that employers are key components of higher education school stakeholders as they are interested towards qualified and academically sound students having tremendous potential and quality to work for their organizations. Maxwell et al., 2008 discusses that “employers” are deemed as having major roles in developing a graduate in higher education as they are in the position to understand the “employability skills” necessary in the market to develop skilled and competent resources

The higher education school’s faculty role would be crucial in developing “**human intellectual capital**” for nation and industries to innovate and discovery in pursuit of excellency of management practices (pffefer and fong , 2004) . The higher education faculties occupy a dominant stake in the higher education school.

2.8 Stakeholder Analysis with references to x College Table 1.

Stakeholder	Wish to Influence		Power to Influence	
	Comment	Score	Comment	Score
Students	The students in the college sector tend to be from different financial backgrounds. They continually make demands that enable them to have an easier life.	High	The college will allow itself to be influenced by the student's demands as long as they do not affect its ability to maintain quality and operate at a profit	Low
Prospective students	Desires to get more admission and financial aids and scholarships	High	The college has its own criteria to select and admit students and distribute scholarship	Low
Board of Governors or Guarantors	The Board of Governors		The work of college is overseen by BoD of trustee who are entirely responsible and top-level managers formulating policies and strategy	High
Senior Management		Low	Senior management is responsible to implement the Board of Governors policies and strategies in action	High
Teachers /Lecturers	The teachers and lecturers want more pay and more personal growth training and development opportunity	High	The teacher union genuine issues are addressed by senior management	Medium
HIGHER EDUCATION IN NEPALBased Non-Teaching Staff	Additional responsibility, pay hike and opportunity for personal growth and development	High	The employee and staff union genuine issues are addressed by senior management	Medium
O'seas Based Non-Teaching Staff				
Parents/guardian	The colleges should provide quality education to their students	High	The college always tries to fulfil parents/guardian wish but, parents and guardians cannot influence college independent working	High
Local Media				
Regional or National media				
Local Education Authority	Wish the college provide quality education and help colleges by providing in their website	High		Low
Other Government authorities				
Hospital	Wish the college helps the international students with General Practioner.	High	The college will help the students to be register with local GP	Low
Banks	Wish the college operates its bank account with the same financial institution	High	In case of any financial issues which might affect the college bank accounts and transaction the bank can always claim legal rights	High
Other Financial institutions				

Major Suppliers	Wish the college always purchase from those suppliers	High	The college might not necessarily choose to purchase from those suppliers if the cost and quality of goods and services are not as expected	Low
Minor Suppliers	Wish the college always purchase from those suppliers	High	The college might not necessarily choose to purchase from those suppliers if the cost and quality of goods and services are not as expected	Low
Educational Consultants	Not applicable			
Local Higher education Community	Wish the college promote their higher education among students	High	The college may or may not promote local higher education	Low
Job agencies				
Railway and Transport	Wish the college helps student to register with them	Low		Low
Local community /Church, Temples, Mosque	The local community wish college encourages students to visits religious centre	Low	The college is independent, student decide to go or not	Low
Investors and Shareholders				
Industrial and Management experts				
Landlords and accommodation providers				

2.9 Main operational process

Marketing and promotional campaign

The colleges and universities do a marketing campaign throughout a year in order to get the good student to be admitted into their colleges.

Admission process

The colleges and universities collect a large number of students academic certificates and credentials and related documents has to be brought to university premises and the responsible department will look after such documents, or may be now students can apply online and attach the related educational documents.

Induction

Once the students join the colleges or the university, a familiarization and induction go on for about minimum 2 weeks the aim of such program is to ensure the students to have built good rapport and relationships with faculty, facilities, organization as well as local culture which they need to know during their time of study.

Teaching and Learning stage

Involves designing and developing academic calendar

The teaching and learning stages in the colleges and university follows the pattern of Blooms Ladder hierarchy the library and self-study hours are also important in higher learning.

Research, Evaluation and application stage, Publication works

The colleges and university assist the student and scholar and researchers to undertake their research works and publication in different subject areas of study.

Student services

The student services are open throughout the year as the sole aim and objectives of student center is facilitate and help students to solve their issues while they are in the study mode.

Annual events and activities

The academic institutions are social laboratory and a multicultural person gets an opportunity to meet each other, not only colleges and universities teaches but also conducts annual events like cultural program, annual sports meets and competition to enable the students and motivate them.

Convocation and award ceremony

For those who have graduated from the universities will be invited to attend the Graduation Ceremony annually to formally and officially handover the students with convocation and degree awards by the institutions. Such ceremony is organized annually by the higher educational establishments.

Job Placement and Internship Program

For those students wishing to have job opportunities are well recognized by the college and universities and career and services center help the students by bringing the different corporate and multinational corporations in their premises so that students wishing to apply for the job can actually interact with each other.

2.10 International Higher education league table

The higher education rankings have been a major debate about around the academic circles, as argued by (Mills et al., 2006) as mushrooming of league tables, industry monitors and ranking of higher education as an attempt to drag attention to their external target markets and stakeholders. (Bickerstaffe and Ridgers, 2007, p. 65) opine that higher education rankings have been criticized as “a kind of democracy in the management development industry” involving various mix. Welch, (2002) termed higher education ranking as “distorting and diminishing the value of higher education”

Yee, 2004 cited in Free et al., 2009 presented that at one instance during September 2004, Harvard and Wharton Higher education decided not to provide information to news and media house publishing higher education rankings and did not wish to provide the alumni and current students detail to higher education week.

Higher education Rankings as discussed by Siemens et al., (2005) Siemens et al., (2005) points that “ranking” of Higher education is one of the important determinant factors in students’ minds while taking the graduate and enrolling in such graduates’ programs. As Williams (2001) cited in Siemens et al., (2005) claims that when the schools’ rankings improved the enrolment rose up by 40%. Corley and Gioia (2000) argue that “competitive “ingredients were added to US B-School by the “higher education ranking” which has led to higher education substantial improvements and their level of performances.

As Guardian online (2010) publish the university league table based on the following factors

1. satisfied with teaching – percentage of students satisfied with teaching
2. satisfied with feedback –percentage of students satisfied with feedback
3. spending per student- how much does a university spends per students in terms of resources and materials
4. student /Staff ratio- The number of students handled by a staff
5. Career Prospects – The job prospects and possibility in terms of returned benefits as salary, recognition among employer
6. Value added score – how colleges and universities add values in Higher education in Nepal

[Adapted from <http://www.guardian.co.uk/education/table/2009/may/12/university-guide-business-management-studies>],

While Sunday times university ranking is bit different as the factors taken into consideration to determine the league table are

1. Student satisfaction
2. Heads /peer assessment – head teacher opinion about course quality and academics opinion about course quality.
3. Research Quality – the research work assessments
4. A/AS Higher-level points – number of applicants entering college or university holding A and AS levels
5. Employment -
6. Degree Awarded – how many have been awarded with 2:1 degree
7. student Staff ratio – number of students attended by number of staff
8. Dropout rate – the students leaving the university.

[adapted from : <http://extras.timesonline.co.uk/stug/universityguide.php?sort=HEADS> ,
http://www.timesonline.co.uk/tol/life_and_style/education/sunday_times_university_guide/article2497779.ece

Similarly, Financial Times (FT.com) online rankings for global MBA program takes into account following factors.

1. Current salary
2. Increment in salary
3. Placement success rank
4. Alumni recommended rank
5. International Faculty
6. International Students
7. International mobility rank
8. International experiences rank
9. Faculty with doctorate
10. Doctoral rank
11. Research rank

Adapted from <http://rankings.ft.com/exportranking/global-mba-rankings/pdf>

2.11. Total Quality Management models in Higher education

While there has been a paradigm shift in the way of acquiring “conventional” ways of higher education in higher education to modern and contemporary education dominated by “services quality” as integral components of higher education schools(Ho and Wearn, 1995) while students are being referred as “customers” it has become customary to jot down the importance of services quality to higher education as “modern customers (referred to students) comes to university not only to acquire knowledge in sophisticated ways of life , they influence the university ranking leagues which might affects the colleges and university enrolments (Williams , 2001)

In this context Parshuraman et al., (1985) have proposed the service quality models in which could be borrowed to apply in the higher education school in determining the various “gaps” which might affect the quality at higher education.

Gap 1. Management perceptions of customer’s expectations and expected services: In terms of higher education where students expect “corporate houses visits and integral to their course of study. The Management might think that a case study of corporate houses will be effective for students.

Gap 2. Management perceptions of customer’s expectations vs service quality specification. For e.g.

In higher education the students would prefer to have flexible attendances policy which the senior management of higher education are well aware of while specifying the standards on attendance policy senior management may not desire to address such issues as even though it looks small it may have a huge impact. The Quality will be always specified in standards

Gap 3. Service quality specification vs service delivery

For e.g., the higher education has specific mission to provide quality higher education and research quality in their teachings and enhancing higher learning but in reality, the instructors may not deliver courses and materials as specified in higher education school missions and values

Gap 4. service deliver vs external communication to customers

For e.g., a student might have joined the higher education while taking into consideration their promotional campaign and higher education rankings as students services of that higher education being excellent in such cases, if a student’s finds a deviation in suppose let’s say student services delivered it creates this form of gap. To improve such gaps two-way communication and feedback is essential in the due course of time.

Gap 5, customer expected service vs perceived service

If a student is expecting to get a scholarship and if they realize that due to some reasons, they may not get the scholarship this may result in gap.

Let’s discuss the HETQMEX (Higher Education Total Quality Management excellence model proposed by Ho and Wearn (2005).

ServQual

Source: Zeithaml, Parasuraman & Berry, Delivering Quality Service

Figure. 2.1 Service Quality Model adapted from Parshuraman et al., (1985).

Let's discuss the HETQMEX (Higher Education Total Quality Management excellence model proposed by Ho and Wearn (2005)

In order to implement the HETQMEX in any higher education needs to establish their objectives in terms of mission statements such as research excellence and grooming higher education leaders. As all people transcending the higher education school should be committing to this mission. The role of senior management is key to improving quality in higher education hence initiation of leadership quality and cultures is utmost important in any higher education schools. Next thing is application of lean management concepts in the higher education school offerings trying to remove any "Muda" and unwanted process, elements from higher education schools.

The standardization and benchmarking quality practices of higher education ought to be based on known or recognized leaders then developing a quality circle to with objective to prevent defects in quality and quality control based on such bench marking practices. Developing a quality check document and building a PDCA cycle (Plan –do –check- Act) to ascertain quality in different intervals of time.

3. Research Design and Methodology

For the mentioned purpose the qualitative data were collected from the college authority and colleges official documents. The researchers collected the secondary sources of data from the college and other related sources of where credible information could be obtained.

3.1 Definition: Literature review

Hart (2003) argues that review of the existing sources of literature entire ranges of published and unpublished data's, information and evidences expressing views and analysis over the nature of topic and method of investigation and evaluation of available documents in relationship to proposed research (Hart, 2003, 13).

3.2 Empirical Research Design and Methodology

Vaus (2001, 16) while we are dealing with research design a researcher need to be clear that Research design is not about some specific methods of data's collection or collection of any particular data. Research design in principle can chose to use any form of data collection either it could be quantitative data or qualitative methods. Hence "Research design refers to structure of an inquiry; it is logical matter rather that logistical one. It is important for Research that while designing research a researcher must identify the specific ranges and types of data and evidences which will answers the research questions in rational and convincing manner (DeVaus, 2001).

(Rajendar Kumar, 2008, 4) argue that research methods could means application and usage of all available methods and techniques which are essential for conducting research. (Rajendra Kumar, 2008, 4) defines that "Research methodology is way to systematically solve the research problems. It may be understood as science of studying how research is done scientifically."

3.3. Qualitative Methods

Prasad and Prasad (2002) argue that various authors have stated that qualitative research method used in research can substantially contribute to provide valuable insights which helps both the researchers and management practitioners to better understand the research issues (Cassell, 2006). Rajendra Kumar (2008,8) argues that Qualitative research deals with qualitative phenomenon in relation with involving quality or kind. Patton (2002, 4) that it is important to define criteria to judge the quality of qualitative data

The skills and experiences of researcher is prominent to qualitative research as "much skillful, sensitive the researcher is the data quality collected may be high (Patton, 2002,11). The prerequisite of Qualitative inquiry is "content analysis" which means it's an ability to extract meaning and figure out data's substantive relationship and not just reading to see what is there. "Qualitative inquiry is especially powerful as a source of grounded theory, theory that is inductively generated from fieldwork, that is theory that emerges from researcher observations and interviews out in the real world rather than in laboratory or the academy" (Patton, 2002, 11) some of the advantages of qualitative methods is that researchers get an opportunity to study issues in depth and also from few interviews and case study. The validity, reliability and credibility of Qualitative methods depends large extent to skill, competence and personal qualities of researcher (for e.g., Personal life of researcher, e.g., Current situation of researcher in their personal life) which might be constraints to qualitative study (Patton, 2002, 14).

The Different kinds of Qualitative Data's

3.4.1. Interviews

The interviews could be held with Open –ended questions which are aimed to attain an in-depth response to the subject matter in terms of people experiences, their perceptions, knowledge, and feelings.

3.4.2. Observations

This are field visits activity and description about the situations, context, environment, mode of thinking and patterns, organizational culture, conversations, behavior, layout and structure and spaces, actions, interpersonal interactions, organizations or community process etc.

These are document in forms of written materials and other documents from institutions and other credible, valid and reliable sources such as organization policy documents, procedural manual, letters and credentials, publication and reports, meetings minutes, artistic works, personal diaries organizational emblem, logo, photographs and feedback for open ended questions and CDs and ranges of sources materials. Such collected data should be compiled and preserved for researcher purposes [Adapted from Patton, 2002, 4].

3.5. Empirical research

Rajendra Kumar (2008) empirical research is based upon the experiences or observation. This kind of research intends to come up with conclusions based on data which are capable of being by observations or experimental type of research.

3.6 Data Collection methods

Data collection methods included conducting open ended questions interviews with Director of studies, Principal and Registrar and teaching faculties and students and other people such as academic experts and students. The spontaneous observation methods were also used wherever necessary felt by the researchers.

3.7.1 Open ended question interview

As suggested by the name itself, an open-ended questionnaire interviews methods of data collection are designed to get in-depth information, experiences and attitudes of individual or groups. Respondent express their views, feeling, experiences and attitudes and practices (in case of organisation, procedures and practices, process) in their own words as there is not much choice for selection for respondents (Gliner and Morgan, 2000, 340). The Director/Principal / Registrar and College academic board/ Employees / Teachers / Staffs / Students of the college were interviewed in regards to their colleges “quality management” how they actually manage highest quality and what do they think is most important in higher education school as matter “managing total quality”. The director was interviewed 3-4 through times and the responses were noted down for further analysis.

3.7.2 Face to face interview

(Kothari, 2008, 97) These types of interviews are mostly begun by the interviewer which is most suitable for intensive and in-depth investigation in an individual or group set up. As argued by (Kothari, 2008, 98) the non-structure interviews format and methods of data collection allowed the researcher greater freedom in terms of putting supplement questions and omit some questions if unnecessary. The qualitative data from these types of interviews has substantially helped the researchers to have collected first-hand information,

3.7.3. Unstructured observation:

Seale and Barnard (1998, 71) argue that in unstructured observations no attempt is made before the observation sessions. The observer has to be prepared to observe anything and everything. Seale and Barnard (1998, 71) the unstructured observations are richer than structured observations. These case study choses unstructured observations as prominent the “Total Quality Management in higher education also depends on the surrounding environment, the colleges building, premises and facility are located and the physical condition and surrounding environment. observation have been recorded and captured by the researchers in the photographs and notes.

3.7.4. Online secondary sources

In this research work data’s have been also collected from the different online and web-based sites of colleges, university and related institution s. with this research work.

3.7.5 Experts Opinion

The view point of experts is deemed necessary to enlighten this research work title “TQM in higher education schools” as scholars’ academicians have been contacted through email, telephone and their views have been incorporated in this research works.

3.7.6. Population and sample size

Cohen et al. (2007, 100) argues sampling issues is related with defining the population on which the result lies. A sampling is essential element of research. Due to many factors and reasons such as the entire population could not be taken into research a small group of population needs to be identified to carry out the research. Since this study is case study based on a higher education college, not all colleges and universities could be studied the detail study of the colleges have been chosen as sample.

3.7.7 Analysis, Summary and findings.

This session discusses about the review of existing literature, research design and methodology and findings drawn on the basis of “TQM Components and Models” and the real data and first-hand information available from the ranges of sample and its population. From this study various prominent and mandatory issues have been analyzed below:

4. Findings at X-Higher College - A Case Study.

This session entails the major findings of a case study undertaken at x higher college considering the mandatory elements and components of “TQM” in higher education as integral to this study. The following is a summary of discussion of a “TQM” higher education’s key elements;

4.1 Mission, Vision Statement and research excellence

Mission statements are the basic purpose for the existence of higher learning institution. The mission statement is deliberately defined and plays a significant role in quality management in higher learning higher education schools. “The mission of the University of Cambridge is to contribute to society through the pursuit of education, learning, and research at the highest international levels of excellence”. “The school is dedicated to developing a new generation of higher education leaders and entrepreneurs, and conducting research not only into the nature of business, but the connections between higher education and the wider world” <http://www.sbs.ox.ac.uk/Pages/default.aspx>.

The mission statement of X higher college is to “establish as a remarkable institution within the South Asia by providing quality education and research in the frontier and to contribute skilled human resources primarily towards national development”. The college should reconsider its mission and vision statement by integrating academic excellence through latest modern – technologies and artificial intelligence as well as exquisite research endeavors.

4.2 Developing Faculties and pool of experts

As established by the literature review in any higher education the role of faculty is utmost important to determine the quality levels of teaching and learning. The X higher education college faculty recruitment policy and committee has clear guidance spread over many stages such as aim of the faculty hiring policy is finding the people with outstanding professional and personal qualities which could be justified through the identification of the job, job specification and job advertisement and interviews, acceptance, review and follow up and monitoring and evaluation by Principal.

4.3 Accreditation bodies and policies

In order to ensure highest level of learning and maintaining the levels of quality educational authority and regulatory body’s role is substantial to enhancing quality assurance and benchmarking in educational sector. The college is

currently offering courses accredited by the Tribhuvan University, Purbanchal University. The college is strictly abided upon the universities policies and frameworks with regards to higher education quality policies and have functional “Board of Directors(BoD) ” BoD entrusted “College Management Committee” having a diversified representative members from within and outside the educational institution, “Academic Audit Committee (AAC)” Independent “Internal Quality Assurance Committee (IQAC) responsible for monitoring , control , assurance , developing policies and frameworks and evaluation of for the smooth operational processes ” it has formed several other committees and sub committees as prescribed in university charter and policy documents. The necessary health and safety and important information are exhibited and put off in college’s wall and nook and corner wherever necessary to provide information and quality assurance is done through student satisfaction surveys.

The college has begun accreditation certification process from University Grant Commission -Nepal (UGC-Nepal) and abiding the necessary quality directives and frameworks as prescribed by UGC-Nepal.

4.3 Student services

The colleges offer the academic as well non-academic student services to students in terms of issuing the different letters to open bank account, The colleges regularly offer supporting English classes, Personality development and free higher education tips and C.V and job interviews skills to student who are seeking such assistance as the students are from outside KTM valley and trying to get some jobs in the city.

4.4 Diversity and Inclusion

The colleges have an adopted a “non-discrimination” principle of human rights and has documented in its official “equal opportunity policy” for every personnel associated and with the college.

4.5 Culture of continuous improvement and quality circles

The principle of continuous improvements is key to total quality management and has led the subject developed till today. The colleges provide ample information in their premises about health and safety measures such as “preventing fire and escaping fire in colleges”, The information in relation to first aid, the information in regards to usage of computers and machinery and dealing the emergency situations are provided in the public and accessible places to all. The public notices which are published with a view to assist and benefits a general public are posted in college walls and room.

4.6 Resources focused to students and curriculum

In this concern as most of the student are from within the country, the colleges senior management authority is involved in finding the marketing opportunities for their course abroad by taking into consultation the educational links and networks and necessarily shape the course and program they will offer the student to staff ratio is approximately 1:25 which is quite a good in terms of numbers of staffs attending the students.

4.7 Learning centers

The college has a plan to develop such centers in a near future as it is now rigorously focusing on the international marketing in recruiting the students. It has recently planned to run “English, Nepali speaking clubs and programs” in South Asian Countries to help and facilitate the quality learning to students while they arrive in Nepal. At the moment an independent library, materials and access to over 50 online journals to enhance the learning for students.

4.8 Stakeholder management

The stakeholder theories and their relative importance to the higher education have been a major concern for higher education schools. The stakeholders could be anyone having a stake or interest in the higher education from institutions to individuals. The different stakeholders have different needs towards organization.

4.9 Job Prospects and job placement

X college has plan to tie up with prospective employers from abroad as well as inside Nepal in order to facilitate the students in getting the job.

4.10 International mobility program and global higher education leaders

The higher education has gone multicultural and in order to respond to the multicultural and global world, the contemporary higher education is offering the international cultural and global mobility program to their MBA candidates which means those students will be able to identify and try to mingle with global workforce and global customers.

4.11 Dropout rate

The x college there are 3% of drop outs as it is at present looking to recruit only merit candidates and quality students who have strong passion and determination to become a future leader.

4.12 Student satisfaction

After every semester break the colleges holds an internal survey about the college's facilities. In an interview with college academic board, it was found that not only the student satisfaction means on the usage of resources and facility. The college's board is committed to sow the "cooperative culture" among people to people and the extra-curricular activities which they believe enhances the creativity of everyone.

4.13 Spending per students

It was found that with a good library, good computer per students (1:8) and investments in information and booklets to students and provision of Virtual Learning Environment demands an adequate spending per students.

4.14 Documentation and follow up

In regards to records and information management of students and related people the colleges follow the due process that should not mean it takes a long time. In order to avoid chaos and confusion the colleges apply Deming PDCA cycle (Plan, Do, check, Act) as college's administration is fully aware of their international students and if there some errors it takes a long time to overcome such errors. Hence proper documentation has to be done to ensure and win the international student.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The main purpose of the higher educational institution as suggested by Blooms Taxonomy is creation of highly valuable knowledge for the society considering this statement, the holistic study of TQM with references to higher learning and concludes that the TQM in higher education in the contemporary context is complex as higher education operates in the open system with society and their external factors affects the higher education school operations.

The faculty, students need, and the modern infrastructure are the most prominent sources of quality and learning in higher learning "Zero Defects" and philosophy of doing right things at once and developing recruitment practices to get "right person at right time for right job" is key to improving quality in Higher education in Nepal.

The introduction of higher education rankings and league table have become pushing factor to improve quality and performances in academic institutions hence such rankings are essential in Nepal but too much market driven league table and higher education rankings might distort the image of higher education in the eyes of their students if any promises remain unfulfilled to large extent of students.

5.2 Recommendations to college

The college should focus on developing new courses based on research, highlight on extracurricular and learnings. The college should cooperate with international research-based agencies to foster innovative learning and integrate Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the learning and educational process.

Lastly the TQM issues are never ending and exhaustive as they get evolved a period of time the aim of TQM program of higher education should continuous improvements and quality as “need” and creation of quality environment in which it operates.

References

Aninnos. L.N. (2007), “The archetype of excellence in universities and TQM”. *Journal of Management History*. Vol .13. No. 4. pp-307-321.

Bowden, J. and Marton, F. (1998), *The University of Learning: Beyond Quality and Competence in Higher Education*, Kogan Page, London.

Blackmore, J. (2002), “Globalization and the restructuring of higher education for new knowledge economies: new dangers or old habits troubling gender equity work in universities?”, *Higher Education Quarterly*, Vol. 56 No. 4, pp. 419-41. cited in SeaLaw (2010)

Bogue, E.G. (1998), “Quality assurance in higher education: the evolution of systems and design ideals”, *New Directions for Institutional Research*, Vol. 99, pp. 7-18.

Boje, D. (2001), “Report from the Division Chair”, *Academy of Management Research Methods Division Newsletter*, Vol. 16 No. 2, Fall.

Cohen, L. , Manion, L. , Morrison, K . Morrison, K.R.B .(2007) “Research methods in education”6th Edition illustrated, Routledge. Available URL: http://books.google.com/books?id=i-YKkgtngiMCandpg=PA102anddq=population+and+sample+size+in+researchandhl=enandei=EMiTazqNIqIhQeehKy4Dgandsa=Xandoi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=10&ved=0CFYQ6AEwCQ#v=onepage&q=population%20and%20sample%20size%20in%20research&f=false

Cassell , C . et al., (2006) . “The role and status of qualitative methods in management research: an empirical account”. *Management Decision* .Vol. 44 .issue 2. pp.290-303

Kothari, C.R. (2008) . “Research Methodology : Methods And Techniques”2nd Edition, New Age International. http://books.google.com/books?id=8c6gkbKi-F4C&pg=PA95&dq=data+collection+methods&hl=en&ei=of8hTeH_HoSohAej_d24Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=1&ved=0CC4Q6AEwADgK#v=onepage&q=data%20collection%20methods&f=false

Gliner, J.A. and Morgan, G.A(2000).”Research methods in applied settings: an integrated approach to design and analysis”Editionillustrated, Publisher, Routledge. Available URL : http://books.google.com/books?id=spywIgzp4vwC&pg=PA340&dq=open+ended+question+interviews+in+research&hl=en&ei=WvQhTfe8GsmWhOfTgOm4Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=1&ved=0CCUQ6AEwAA#v=onepage&q=open%20ended%20question%20interviews%20in%20research&f=false

Hart, C. (2003) “Doing a literature review: releasing the social science research”Edition reprint SAGE. Available URL: http://books.google.com/books?id=FkXvY8oDFdsC&printsec=frontcover&dq=importance+of+literature+review+in+research&hl=en&ei=WAohTa_1J5KGhQe5gp23Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=1&ved=0CCcQ6AEwAA#v=onepage&q=importance%20of%20literature%20review%20in%20research&f=false

De Vaus, D.A (2001). *Research design in social research*. Research Methods series . Illustrated Reprint , Sage 2001. Available URL:

http://books.google.com/books?id=wImwZZXzPlkC&pg=PA8&dq=definition+of+research+design&hl=en&ei=McYgTajqDYmZhQeB9sS4Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=7&ved=0CEUQ6AEwBg#v=onepage&q=definition%20of%20research%20design&f=false

Mouton J and M arais H C 1996. *Basic concepts in the methodology of the social sciences*. Revised edn. Pretoria: Human Sciences Research Council

Prasad, A. and Prasad, P. (2002), “The coming age of interpretive organizational research”, *Organizational Research Methods*, Vol. 5 No. 1, pp. 4-11.

Sea Law, D.C . (2010) . “Quality assurance in post-secondary education Some common approaches”. *Quality Assurance in Education* Vol. 18 No. 1, 2010 . pp. 64-77

Weinrach , J. (2004) “The business of educating”. *Environmental Quality Management*, 14, 1; ABI/INFORM Globalpg. 91

Richardson, J.T.E. (2000), *Researching Student Learning: Approaches to Studying in Campus-based and Distance Education*, SRHE and Open University Press, Buckingham.

Patton, M.C (2002) “Qualitative research and evaluation methods”. 3rd Edition, illustrated, reprint SAGE, 2002. Available URL :

http://books.google.com/books?id=FjBw2oi8El4C&printsec=frontcover&dq=qualitative+methods+in+research&hl=en&ei=PiMhTZ7KIoWSHAecvvG2Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=8&ved=0CFEQ6AEwBw#v=onepage&q&f=false

Tam, M. (2001), “Measuring quality and performance in higher education”, *Quality in Higher Education*, Vol. 7 No. 1, pp. 47-54.

Peters, M. (2004), “Higher education, globalization and the knowledge economy”, in Walker, M. and Nixon, J. (Eds), *Reclaiming Universities from a Runaway World*, SRHE and Open University Press, Buckingham cited in Sealaw (2010)

Harvey, L. and Knight, P.T. (1996), *Transforming Higher Education*, SRHE and Open University Press, Buckingham

Susan E. Pariseau, J.R. McDaniel, (1997) "Assessing service quality in schools of business", *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*, Vol. 14 Iss: 3, pp.204 - 218

Rajendar Kumar. Research Methodology. Publisher APH Publishing ISBN8131304221.

http://books.google.com/books?id=7btTIFXBRnoC&printsec=frontcover&dq=definition+of+research+methodology&hl=en&ei=HtAgTcaLIsKJhQerwMi3Dg&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=1&sqi=2&ved=0CCgQ6AEwAA#v=onepage&q=definition%20of%20research%20methodology&f=false

Seale, J. and Barnard, S. (1998). “Therapy research processes and practicalities” illustrated edition, Elsevier Health Sciences.

http://books.google.com/books?id=ucmN_TcWiv0C&pg=PA71&dq=unstructured+observations&hl=en&ei=UjQiTb0hybSEB8_s9bYO&sa=X&oi=book_result&ct=result&resnum=2&ved=0CCwQ6AEwAQ#v=onepage&q=unstructured%20observations&f=false

[University Grants Commission Nepal 2023. \(ugcnepal.edu.np\)](http://ugcnepal.edu.np)

ABSTRACT

Purpose

The higher learning and academic research are critical to every sphere of human life. The quality issue in the higher learning is of public interest as academic institutions are integral and core elements constituting of scholars and the

manifestation of educational quality is of interest to public and regulatory bodies that supports universities through funding and support.

Colleges and universities have been significant in fostering skilled human resource development, innovation in technology and purely academic research about social engineering and other multi-discipline, modern society have universally accepted academic institutions for teaching and learning in general as well as specific disciplines of knowledge. Contemporarily Change Management discipline at colleges and university have become critical as the academic institutions are subjects to intensified competition and changing macro environmental scenarios, “managing total quality” to “Just” the academic institutions basic reason for existence i.e., “purpose”.

The basic purposes of this study are reviewing “Total Quality Management” literature, purification of Quality thoughts (analytical insight) and developing a framework of total quality management system and application of such TQM Principles and framework into the higher education to evaluate and appraise the higher education quality system and recommend some measures.

Design/methodology/approach – An exploratory and analytical case study have been carried out at x the higher education school in Nepal. The case study consists of detail examining the operational process at x Higher education College. The analytical case study was carried out to find out the Quality Policy, their official documentation, and implementing mechanism to have thorough views and sounds understanding of the quality systems at the specific college. The primary and secondary interviews were held with key figures of the colleges as well as staffs from different regions and departments. Various Quality components that have been thought and discussed by authors in relations to “Managing Total Quality” in higher education have been disintegrated into smaller forms and elements to have minute understanding of the college quality operational system and reviewed such operations of college to evaluate and appraise TQM at college

Based on the literature review The Total Quality Framework for the higher education was established and college quality management system is assessed and evaluated with existing Total Quality management principles and practices.

Findings – The comparative analysis of quality management system at X Higher education indicates that there are important improvements opportunities in anticipating potential students for a college and in terms of generating effective customer services.

Research Limitations/implications – This is case study carried out at x higher education schools.

Practical implications – This study is specifically focuses on the application of Total Quality Management principles and practices to help evaluate quality system of x higher education which would in-turn help to improve the quality at higher education in Nepal and identifying various quality components of higher education. This would also enable the colleges to improve an operations and procedure that are directly or indirectly affects quality and develop quality environment at higher education schools.